

Half-Height Double-Row CFET Standard Cells for Area Optimized Placement in A7 CMOS Node

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Abstract—Complementary FET (CFET) is a promising device architecture that proceeds the CMOS scaling during the post-nanosheet device era. Among several CFET variants, Double-Row (DR) CFET further enables 15% track height scaling on standard cells, by sharing a middle row of vias, while sustaining an optimized Middle-Of-Line (MOL) process complexity. In this study, half-height double-row (hDR) CFET is proposed as a highly practical and impactful design style to overcome the cell and block level limitations of DR CFET architecture. First, hDR CFET introduces a high flexibility on standard cell layout design with significant area optimization. Secondly, hDR cell insertion in the backend physical design flow further optimizes the cell placement, and recovers block level area scaling to match the cell height scaling. Results on A7 CFET technology library show area reduction up to 50% on standard cell layouts. Moreover, block level PnR results after enabling only 6 types of hDR cells in standard cell library show 10% of area scaling on ARM Cortex-M0 32-bit core at 90% utilization, proving the strength of the concept. Finally, 14% of block level area scaling is further projected for an enriched standard cell library with an extended set of hDR cells.

Index Terms—Double-Row CFET, CMOS scaling, technology node, standard cell library, placement, physical design, design technology co-optimization.

I. INTRODUCTION

Innovative device architectures, process flows and a diversity of materials are being proposed for the continuation of CMOS scaling beyond FinFET nodes [1]–[9]. A representative CMOS scaling roadmap is shown in Fig. 1. Beyond today’s commercially available N3 FinFET node, top-tier foundries are announcing for their volume production plans on Gate-all-around (GAA) nanosheet devices starting at N2/18A process technology node [10], [11]. For return of investment profitability, N2 introduction node is expected to be followed by at least 2 consecutive nodes, i.e. scaled A14 nanosheet and extended A10 forksheet nodes [12]. Furthermore, several scaling boosters such as nanosheet/forksheet width modulation [13], backside power delivery network (BSPDN) options [14]–[16], metal gate cut and self-aligned block [17] have been presented to reinforce the device architectural change to its best. Beyond nanosheet nodes, the first introduction of Complementary FET (CFET) device architecture [18]–[21] is foreseen around A7 technology node, where n- and p-type FET devices are stacked on top of each other for further power, performance and area (PPA) improvement towards the ultimate CMOS scaling.

Fig. 1. CMOS scaling roadmap along FinFET to nanosheet and CFET nodes.

In literature, several CFET variants had been investigated in recent years from the point of PPA scaling, process complexity, manufacturability and cost. [22] analyses several CFET structures such as split versus merged local interconnect, and split- versus common-gate in terms of layout impacts and cost. [23] compares monolithic and sequential integration aspects of CFET, and investigates MOL innovations such as BSPDN connection schemes and Vertical-Horizontal-Vertical (VHV) routing style in standard cells. [24] presents an extensive materials to system co-optimization study on logic and SRAM bit-cells, covering super-via versus direct-backside-connection for power and signal, split- versus common-gate, and frontside (FS) and backside (BS) PDN combinations. [25] focuses on BS power delivery and signaling trade-offs for PowerVia and backside gate contact. [26] presents a comparative study between FinFET, nanosheet and CFET devices from standard cell level to block level. Finally, [27] presents a comprehensive CFET design technology co-optimization (DTCO) study covering device level, standard cell library, block level and SRAM bit-cell benchmarks on a proposed Double-Row (DR) CFET architecture with a PowerWall (PWW) power option. DR CFET enables 15% cell height scaling on standard cells, by taking advantage of a shared middle row of vias (MRW) for top-bottom device connection with a lower Middle-Of-Line (MOL) process complexity than its single-row (SR) CFET version. On the other hand, the double-row cell layout configuration was causing considerable area inefficiencies in several standard cells due to unused silicon area and/or extra inactive dummy gates. As a result, cell level area inefficiencies were impacting and obstructing the core area scaling potential

at block level.

In this study, we propose a novel and powerful design style, i.e. *half-height double-row (hDR) CFET* that has a two-fold innovation:

- 1) optimizes the aforementioned layout area inefficiencies on DR CFET standard cells, e.g. up to 50% in certain cells,
- 2) unlocks the block level scaling potential to achieve lower core area, matching the cell height scaling, e.g. up to 15% in DR CFET with PowerWall option.

Rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II summarizes the background and motivation behind this study. Section III introduces the proposed hDR CFET architecture, and details its enablement at cell and block levels. Section IV explains our methodology and benchmarks. Section V presents the experimental results at cell, library and block levels. Finally, Section VI concludes the paper with a summary of messages.

II. BACKGROUND AND MOTIVATION

Cross-sectional view of the common-gate DR CFET architecture [27] with a cell height (CH) of $2 \times 69nm$ (targeted for A7 technology node) is shown in Fig. 2. DR CFET encapsulates two pairs of CFETs as the building primitive for logic design, where the middle column of M0 and MRW are shared between two rows of CFETs. B/MD layers are backside and frontside device metal contacts to source and drain regions, respectively. In this instance of DR CFET, each n/pFET device has 2 vertically stacked sheets with 19nm of active width per sheet, 9nm of B/MD extension and 12nm of gate extension on +/- y-axis. Pitch/critical dimension (cd) values are 19nm/11nm and 34.5nm/20nm for frontside M0 and backside BM0, respectively. DR CFET architecture has a total of 7 tracks of M0 at frontside, and a total of 4 tracks of BM0 at backside, where each CFET pair has effectively 3.5 tracks of FS M0 and 1 track of BS BM0 for n/pFET devices, respectively. 2 out of 7 M0 tracks (dashed orange) at cell edges are reserved for routing purpose in PnR, which effectively leaves 5 tracks of M0 for standard cell internal routing. Similarly, 2 out of 4 BM0 tracks (dashed gray) are reserved for global VDD power and VSS ground (PG) rails at backside, which effectively leaves only 2 tracks of BM0 for backside signal routing. Finally, PowerWalls (blue) at cell edges function as local VSS rails to shorten the distance of top NFET device to VSS ground potential, hence are intended to improve IR drop.

At cell level, it was shown in [27] that DR CFET architecture imposes certain limitations on standard cell layout design, although it achieves 15% of cell height scaling and 15% of lower MOL process complexity compared to its SR CFET counterpart. Mapping a logic functionality from SR to DR CFET architectural layout template can cause dramatic area overhead in certain standard cells. Especially the primitive cells with a lower drive strength (D) and smaller layout area, such as inverter (INV), buffer ($BUFF$), and (AN), or (OR), nand (ND), nor (NR), etc. are impacted relatively higher, when

Fig. 2. Cross-sectional view of DR CFET architecture with frontside 7T M0 and backside 4T BM0 tracks. MRW functions as a vertical local connection between top and bottom devices as well as a connection between FS and BS BEOL. The annotated numbers indicate the width, spacing or extension of the physical structure in nanometers.

implemented in DR template. Fig. 3 shows an example case of INV and ND cells that are laid out in SR (left column) and DR (right column) templates. Gate, dummy gate, active, MRW, PowerWall and horizontal FS M0 layers are shown from a top layout view. INV and ND require 2 and $3 \times CPP \times CH_{SR}$ area in SR template, where CH_{SR} is 81nm. On the other hand, when those two cells are mapped to DR template, both occupy $2 \times CPP \times CH_{DR}$, where CH_{DR} is 138nm. INV fits into and fills only one half of DR template,

Fig. 3. Remapping logic from SR CFET (left column) to DR CFET (right column) architecture can cause significant area overhead in standard cell layouts, e.g. +70% and +14% higher area in INV and ND cells, respectively.

Fig. 4. Cell height scaling (15%) from SR to DR CFET was invisible at block level core area scaling projections. Extra area overhead that is caused by unused silicon area (2%) and extra dummy gates (12%) in standard cell layouts, results in an overall +2% higher core area on block level projections.

while the other upper half is occupied by nonfunctional and unused silicon area. *ND2D1* requires two extra dummy gates in DR template. Overall, SR to DR transition easily brings 70% and 14% area overhead for the aforementioned cells, respectively [27].

At library level, Fig. 4 shows that the area overhead sourced by unused silicon and extra dummy gates in cells add on top of each other, resulting in an overall 2% higher core area on block level projections. A detailed explanation of our projection methodology is presented in Section IV. To summarize, 15% of CH scaling from SR to DR CFET is completely offset at block level due to DR CFET template, which motivates this study.

To recover the inefficient area usage in DR CFET standard cells, multi-bit and/or multi-functional cell enablement could be a solution, which was already proposed in [27]. However this scenario has two major drawbacks, especially for large commercial libraries with high cell counts. First of all, there exists an enormous amount of possible cell combinations in library design space, which would be impractical at its simplest form. Secondly, design-effort would exponentially grow both for designing such a standard cell library as well as for its characterization, validation and future maintenance. Therefore, this idea quickly turns into insatiable on large commercial standard cell libraries with hundreds of cells.

As an alternative approach to that problem, this study proposes the *half-height double-row CFET cell enablement*, which is explained next.

III. HALF-HEIGHT DOUBLE-ROW CFET CELL ENABLEMENT

hDR CFET cell enablement is composed of two main steps, where the first step is the hDR CFET standard cell design. The second step is the physical design enablement of hDR

Fig. 5. An example of hDR cell enablement over 3 standard cells. For area optimization, 1) standard cells are redesigned and mapped from DR to hDR template, that significantly optimizes each cell's area, e.g. 50% lower area for *INV D1*. Afterwards 2) hDR cells are plugged and placed together while taking care of the shared middle row of MRWs to avoid any overlaps. This example shows a total of 29% lower area for the placed 3 cells.

cell insertion during PnR. Fig. 5 explains the concept of hDR cell enablement over a layout example, where in the top left illustration three standard cells from a DR CFET library, i.e. *INV D1*, *ND2D1*, *OR2D1*, are abutted within an area of $7 \times CPP \times CH_{DR}$ during placement. However, layout area inefficiency of each standard cell adds on top, and overall increases the block level area as explained in the previous section.

A. hDR CFET Standard Cell Design

For a holistic optimization of block level area usage, DR cells can be first redesigned and mapped to hDR template. Fig. 5 shows an example where the hDR versions of the aforementioned cells occupy $2/3/5 \times CPP \times CH_{hDR}$, respectively, where CH_{hDR} is only $1/2 CH_{DR}$, which is $69nm$. As a result, layout conversion from DR to hDR template in this example leads to 50%, 25% and 17% of cell area optimization, respectively. Although hDR template resembles SR template, the major distinction is that hDR template entails the common usage of the shared middle row of MRW resources. That is to say, hDR cell boundary exactly cuts and passes along the middle row of MRWs, while SR cell boundary covers a complete middle track of MRWs. Therefore, SR cells do not require any placement constraints, whereas hDR cells require certain placement directives in PnR, which are explained next.

B. hDR CFET Physical Design Enablement

hDR cell placement strictly depends on the allocation of MRWs on the shared middle row. Fig. 5 shows an example where the hDR versions of *H(INV D1, ND2D1, OR2D1)* are plugged onto each other, and harmoniously placed while any overlapping MRWs are avoided. Consequently, abutted hDR cells fit into an area of $5 \times CPP \times CH_{DR}$, which achieve 29% lower area than using DR template.

Fig. 6. Mixed usage of hDR and DR cells in block level floorplan. A cell row can consist of DR and/or multiple hDR cells.

A generalized block level floorplan view of hDR and DR cell placement is shown in Fig. 6. Cell placement rows are mirrored along the local VSS PowerWalls (blue), that also overlap along the global backside VDD power rails at BM0 (gray). Both DR and hDR cells can be placed on the core area region in a mixed manner, where middle tracks between rails are occupied by MRWs. Although hDR cells are significantly promising in terms of area scaling, hDR cell insertion in PnR has to be automatized in such a way that the EDA tool can handle and place millions of cell instances without any overlapping MRW violations. Therefore, the hDR cell placement problem turns into a MRW allocation challenge, where hDR cells compete to find available positions to be plugged in and placed on canvas.

Edge constraint is a type of physical location directive, that is fed into the EDA tool for legal cell placement in PnR. A cell's edge can be completely or partially constrained by giving start and end points of an edge interval. In this study, x-coordinates of start/end points of MRW polygons are defined as edge constraints for each hDR cell type. Fig. 7 shows the usage of edge constraints (red lines over MRWs on the middle track). In the first example, hDR cells are placed without any MRW conflicts. In the second example, hDR cells initially have conflicting edge constraints due to overlapping MRWs. After the placement optimization, the MRW conflict is resolved, and the cell placement is legalized.

Fig. 7. PnR examples on hDR cell placement. The red lines over MRWs (blue) indicate the edge constraints used for solving MRW conflicts.

IV. METHODOLOGY

This section explains our methodology of standard cell libraries, CPU benchmarks, library level core area scaling projections, and block level PnR experiments.

In this study, standard cell libraries with 25 cell types that cover distinct logic functionalities and drive strengths have been selected. Benchmarking on relatively small libraries provides an advantage of short return time on iterative trials for technology targeting, hence enables rapid DTCO cycles. Cell list consists of *AN*, *OR*, *ND*, *NR*, *AO*, *AOI*, *OA*, *OAI*, *BUFF*, *INV*, *full adder (FA)*, *clock gate (ICG)*, *MUX*, *XOR*, *XNR*, *D-type flip-flops with low asserted re/set (DFF, DFFRL, DFFSL)*. Standard cells are based on A7 SR, DR and hDR CFET architectural templates. Design rules are derived from A7 CFET virtual fab process flow assumptions that are modelled in [28]. Libraries have been first layouted in [29]. Afterwards 3D models for each cell have been constructed with a n-on-p device stack configuration in [30]. TCAD-calibrated BSIM-CMG n/p-channel device models have been targeted for $\sim 0.9nA/device$ leakage current (I_{off}) at $low-V_{th}(lvt) / tt / 0.7V / 25^{\circ}C$ process-voltage-temperature (PVT) corner. Cell RC parasitics have been extracted in [31]. Extracted cell netlists have been characterized in [32], using [33] as the external circuit simulator.

Regarding the CPU benchmarks, two cores have been selected. ARM 64-bit HD core with $\sim 500K-700K$ cells ($\sim 7\%-10\%$ flop rate) for library level core area scaling projections; ARM Cortex-M0 32-bit core with $\sim 15K-20K$ cells ($\sim 5\%-7\%$ flop rate) for block level PnR experiments. Both cores do not include any SRAM macros.

Core area projections at library level apply cell usage statistics from physical implementations (in older nodes) of an ARM 64-bit HD CPU (Armv8 - without SRAM macros). Area of each cell type is weighted by its instance count to calculate the total cell area. As an early technology targeting tool, this approach can conveniently estimate core area scaling between different technology libraries, in consistency with block level PnR runs.

Block level PnR experiments are performed on 32-bit core, by sweeping across wide ranges of frequency and area points to explore a broad perspective on PPA design space. Synthesis and PnR steps of backend physical design have been performed in [34] and [35], respectively.

V. RESULTS

This section presents and discusses results at cell, library and block levels, that are based on A7 CFET SR, DR and hDR standard cell libraries, and block level PnR experiments on CPU benchmarks.

A. Cell level

A direct transition from SR to DR template in standard cell design initially lowers the layout area efficiency in certain cell types as explained in Section II. Fig. 8 shows a cell breakdown of the relative area overhead on DR and hDR libraries in comparison to SR library. It is shown that more complex and

Fig. 8. Relative area overhead in A7 DR and hDR standard cell libraries w.r.t. A7 SR library. Architectural transition from SR to DR template penalizes area of certain cells more. Although many DR cells can still match CH scaling of -15%, cells like *INVDI* (70%), *AN2D1* (28%), *NR2D1* (14%), etc. are severely affected. hDR cell enablement dramatically optimizes cell area, especially on those with the highest area overheads, e.g. -50%, -17%, -25%, respectively.

large cells such as *flops*, *MUX*, *FA*, *ICG*, *AO**, *OA**, etc. are less affected in DR library. Many of those cells achieve even the same level of SR to DR CH scaling (i.e. 15%) at cell level. In contrast, less complex cells with a lower footprint are significantly affected in terms of DR area overhead, e.g. *INVDI* (70%), *AN2D1* (28%), *NR2D1* (14%). Given that such fundamental logic cells are on the basis of logic operations, they can be found in almost all timing paths of a design, and have high instance counts. As a result, individual cell area overheads multiplied by high instance counts quickly accumulate, and diminish the overall scaling advantage of DR template at block level, as already projected in Fig. 4. hDR cell enablement overcomes this problem when applied to DR

library. As a first step of hDR cell enablement in A7 CFET node, DR cells with a high area overhead (i.e. 6 cells in Fig. 8) have been selected and converted to hDR template. Results show significant cell area optimization, e.g. *INVDI* (-50%), *AN2D1* (-17%), *NR2D1* (-25%), etc. As the next step, hDR cells are evaluated at library level.

B. Library level

Core area scaling projections are shown in Fig. 9 for A7 CFET SR, DR and hDR libraries. From A7 SR to DR library, projections show that 15% CH scaling potential of DR library is offset by DR layout limitations such as unused silicon area and/or extra dummy gates. After inserting only 6 types of hDR cells, core area is drastically scaled by -11% in A7 hDR library compared to A7 DR library. Following this observation, set of hDR cells has been extended (from +6 to +10 and +12 cells) to push the library optimization furthermore, by including *H(BUFFD4, INV4, ND2D2, NR2D2)* and *H(AO*)*, respectively. Fig. 9 shows that with increasing number of hDR cells, core area scales down to -14% in A7 hDR (+12 cells). The resulting core area scaling projection reaches -12%, that is much closer to the -15% CH scaling. Moreover, the library delay comparison of 6 hDR cells show an average of 3% lower cell delay than their DR versions. As the next step, hDR libraries are evaluated at block level PnR experiments.

C. Block level

As the second step of hDR cell enablement, edge constraints have been defined for [35]. Fig. 10 shows a snapshot from an ARM Cortex-M0 design after PnR, where three distinct regions are zoomed in. It is shown that hDR cells are utilized at different proportions varying from high to moderate and low density level. In addition, two observations draw attention. First, hDR (green) and DR (brown) cells are efficiently mixed during placement. Secondly, it is noticeable that EDA tool has

Fig. 9. Core area projections at library level, based on cell area scaling in A7 CFET libraries. Incrementing hDR cell types in a library from +6 to +12 cells, further scales the core area from -11% down to -14%.

Fig. 10. Block level PnR snapshots. (left) High, moderate and low density regions of hDR cell usage. (right) A zoom-in view shows that 1. mixed placement of hDR and DR cells are enabled, 2. edge constraints succeed in avoiding any MRW overlaps. The red lines at middle row position represent the edge constraints, where MRWs are physically located in standard cell layouts. Relative position (above/under a cell edge boundary) of an edge constraint determines to which cell it belongs to.

managed to densely plug hDR cells onto each other without any MRW overlaps.

Core area versus utilization is shown in Fig. 11 for ARM Cortex-M0 under 2.44 GHz frequency constraint. The left-most point of each curve indicates the min-area design under the criteria of DRC < 10 and no timing violation. It shows that PnR implementation with A7 hDR (+6 cells) library further pushes the achievable minimum core area down by -10%. Moreover, over 90% utilization is achieved in PnR runs by both A7 CFET libraries. The high utilization shows that hDR cells can be placed densely even with the edge constraints,

Fig. 11. PnR core area vs utilization. A7 hDR (+6 cells) significantly scales core area down by -10% at the achieved minimum core area.

and the degradation of utilization is marginal. However, even though DR designs achieve slightly higher utilization, the areas of unused silicon and dummy gates are also included in the utilization calculation, which inflates the utilization figure. In this case, the area efficiency of the core can be more accurately captured by the active device density, shown in Fig. 12. The highest density achieved by hDR designs is 9% higher than DR designs, exhibiting more efficient usage of core area.

Fig. 12. PnR active device density. A7 hDR (+6 cells) achieves 9% higher active device density than DR design.

Fig. 13. PnR cell counts for 6 types of DR and hDR cells. After hDR cell enablement, EDA tool significantly favours the usage of hDR cells in place of DR cells.

Cell counts for 6 types of (h)DR cells of one design are shown in Fig 13. It is observed that when hDR cells are present and available in A7 hDR (+6 cells) library, hDR cells rather than DR cells are dominantly instantiated. This shows that hDR cells are highly favoured over DR cells in PnR for area optimization. The rare DR instances are instantiated mostly when the space is confined by both the left and right, so that the narrower DR cell can fit in while the corresponding hDR cell cannot. Additionally, the total runtime difference of physical implementation (i.e. floorplanning, placement, clock tree synthesis, routing, etc.) between the minimum area designs when hDR cells are enabled, is observed to be 15% higher due to the presence of edge constraints. In conclusion, the high usage of hDR cells show their power in area optimization while maintaining the design quality of results (QoR).

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This study proposes a novel and powerful technique, i.e. *half-height double-row CFET standard cells and their physical design enablement*, for area optimized placement of standard cells targeting A7 CFET CMOS technology node. The proposed technique has been first introduced over cell layout examples as well as block level floorplan views. hDR cells optimize and improve the overall layout area efficiency at cell, library and block levels. Edge constraint directives are fed into EDA tool for legal cell placement in PnR. Core area scaling projections as well as block level PnR results are showing significant area improvement on library and CPU benchmarks. Finally, this technique foresees further area scaling potential on larger cell libraries with an extended richer set of hDR cells.

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